

A NEW REAGENT FOR THE ESTIMATION OF MERCURY AND COPPER.

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2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine has been found² to be a good reagent for the estimation of mercuric and cupric salts.

It has been shown (Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 244) that alcoholic solution of the sodium salt of 5-thiolacridine derivative reacts with neutral solutions of mercuric chloride and cupric sulphate forming insoluble mercurio-dithio- and cupro-dithioacridines (I, R = Hg or Cu) respectively. This reaction has been utilised for quantitative estimation of mercury and copper in their inorganic as well as organic compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The reagent is to be prepared by dissolving 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiol-

acridine (0.11 g.) in 95-100% alcohol (100 to 150 c.c.) mixed with 3.5 c.c. of *N/10*-alcoholic or aqueous caustic soda solution, and filtering the solution thus obtained. For estimating mercury, the compound is treated with strong or fuming nitric acid or other reagents to convert mercury into its soluble "-ic" form. The solution is then made just alkaline by adding caustic soda or sodium carbonate and then acidified by hydrochloric acid (excess should be avoided). In case of copper, the compound should be digested with little sulphuric acid so that a solution of copper sulphate is obtained.

A solution (about 10 c.c.) containing 10 to 20 mg. of mercury or 5 to 10 mg. of copper is best suitable for estimation. To the neutral solution, excess of the reagent is added and the mixture is to be stirred for some time and allowed to stand for several hours or preferably overnight. The precipitate, yellowish to red in the case of mercury, and pinkish brown in the case of copper, settles down and an orange to reddish supernatant

liquid indicates the excess of the reagent. 101 C.c. reagent is sufficient for 10 mg. of mercury and 5 mg. of copper. The precipitate is then filtered on a Gooch crucible and washed with 95% alcohol till the filtrate becomes almost colourless. The Gooch is dried in a steam oven and weighed. One gram of the precipitate is equivalent to 0.2676 g. of mercury and 0.09286 g. of copper. The copper derivative (I, R=Cu) contains 4 molecules of water of crystallisation. The results obtained are shown in the following table. Samples 1 and 2 were dissolved in strong nitric acid, 4 in fuming nitric acid, 5 and 6 in aqua regia, 7, 9 and 10 in strong sulphuric acid, while samples 3 and 8 were dissolved in water and directly treated with the reagent.

No.	Substance.	Actual wt. taken.	Wt. of ppt.	Metal	
				found.	calc.
1	Mercury metallic ...	0.01128 g.	0.0421 g	99.88%	100%
2	Mercuric oxide ...	0.01505	0.0521	92.40	92.61
3	Mercuric chloride ...	0.01706	0.0471	73.89	73.85
4	Mercuric acetate ...	0.02082	0.0489	62.87	62.96
5	Mercurous chloride ...	0.01665	0.0530	85.19	84.96
6	Mercuric sulphide ...	0.01305	0.0420	86.14	86.24
7	Copper oxide ...	0.00759	0.0653	79.90	79.89
8	Copper sulphate (cryst.) ...	0.01542	0.0418	25.17	25.48
9	Copper acetate (cryst.) ...	0.01248	0.0428	31.84	31.86
10	Copper citrate ...	0.01464	0.0521	33.04	33.47

A freshly prepared solution of the purest sample of 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine (m.p. 244-45°) should always be used. The acridine compound itself is sometimes precipitated due to the evaporation of alcohol or dilution during addition, but this is harmless, as it goes into solution by addition of more alcohol and is completely removed while washing the precipitate. If there is excess of inorganic salts in the solution to be estimated, these may be precipitated during dilution with alcohol, in that case the precipitate should be washed with water after removing the reagent. Acids and alkalis should be used to a minimum in preparing the solution.

The presence of the metals of groups I, II and III interferes with the estimation of copper and mercury. Those of IV and V have no effect. Notwithstanding this limitation, it is an accurate semi-micro method and may have varied applications.

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